

ANALYSIS OF MUSICAL TEXTURES PLAYED ON THE GUITAR BY MEANS OF REAL-TIME EXTRACTION OF MID-LEVEL DESCRIPTORS

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents a set of mid-level descriptors for the analysis of musical textures played on the guitar, divided in six categories: global, guitar-specific, rhythm, pitch, amplitude and spectrum descriptors. The employed system is based on an acoustic fretted nylon string guitar with hexaphonic pick-ups, and was programmed in Max. An overview of the explored low-level audio descriptors is given in the first section. Mid-level descriptors, many of them based on a general affordance of the guitar, are the subject of the central section. Finally, some distinctive characteristics of five different textures – two-voice writing, block chords, arpeggios, fast gestures with legato, slow melody with accompaniment– are highlighted with the help of the implemented tools.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of mid-level acoustic descriptors represents the ongoing stage of a project started a few years ago, based on an acoustic nylon string guitar equipped with hexaphonic pickups, and implemented in real-time in Max. Previous efforts were dedicated to the analysis of different guitar techniques, such as tremolos, block chords, voice/layer balance, and rhythmic phrasing [1, 2].

The main low-level features of guitar sounds may be adequately represented by scalars (single values) associated with one event (a note); this fact makes easier the planning and implementation of mid-level descriptors, since it is not necessary to deal with the comparison of low-level data curves of different lengths. We believe that the combination of a few mid-level descriptors is able to establish a consistent description of different musical segments played on the guitar, what may be useful for later comparisons, and may even lead to some kind of categorization. The computation of these descriptors is made on pre-established segments, which can be worked out by manual or automatic segmentation processes. Despite the existence of segmentation strategies, the excerpts analyzed in this paper were segmented by hand, since they represent typical textures on guitar, extracted from the well-

established repertoire of the instrument. In these cases, the presence of a score facilitates the interpretation of the results and the evaluation of the descriptors' adequacy.

The text is divided in three sections. Firstly, we discuss the low-level descriptors in use, and some sonic features not covered by them. The second section presents and discusses the implementation of mid-level descriptors, which were based on a – somehow hypothetical – general affordance of the guitar, avoiding any particular bias towards specific musical styles. The descriptors were divided in different categories that should not be interpreted as totally independent from each other: global, guitar-specific, rhythm, pitch, amplitude and spectrum descriptors. Finally, we present some musical examples and their corresponding mid-level descriptors. Distinctive values for each chosen texture are discussed. Although the small number of excerpts prevents any kind of generalization, the preliminary results encourage their use in performance analyses. Besides, the implemented mid-level descriptors represent a consistent base for the next stages of the research: expansion of the database, creation of new descriptors, real-time analysis, comparison and classification of musical segments, comparative analysis of a sequence of segments. Upon the latter features, we intend to build a tool for the practice of interactive improvisational music, based on Rowe's player paradigm [3]. A virtual partner, provided with a dedicated nylon guitar samples library, should be able to mimic, and propose variations on the textures played by the guitarist¹. The mid-level descriptors will be also explored in spatialization routines and in interaction with gestural descriptors.

2. LOW-LEVEL DESCRIPTORS

Every note event, within a specific musical segment, is defined by the following parameters: event number; time of the event (onset or offset); number of the string in use; fundamental frequency; amplitude; spectral centroid; slur flag; presence of bend or vibrato.

The time of the occurrence of the event, measured from the beginning of the segment, is expressed in milliseconds. The detection of onsets and offsets are described in [1],

¹ At this writing, the system is based on a Spanish acoustic guitar Alhambra and LR Baggs pickups. Two features of this hardware –the significant influence of one string on the remaining ones, and a remarkable timbral difference between the acoustic sound and the picked up signal– have pushed us towards a more symbolic approach, instead of using the direct audio as the starting material for interactive processes.

within an error margin of 10 ms. Concerning the string choice, it is worth remembering that the guitar strings are numbered from 1 to 6, from high to low.

For the extraction of the fundamental frequencies and its variations we use the object *fiddle*, created by M. Puckette [4]. The fundamental frequency is expressed in Midi notes, quantized to integers. The exact tuning of the instrument is a pre-requisite to a correct extraction of frequency deviations, such as vibratos and bends, which are expressed with floating point values. Note that we do not use *fiddle*'s own attack detection; when our system detects an onset, it waits for a short period (ca. 50–60 ms) before requesting a reliable fundamental frequency. Some onsets are detected without a definite frequency. In these cases, they are named non-pitched events, and receive a very high fixed value (120). The same values calculated on the onset for the fundamental frequency are stored to be used in the corresponding offset event. The offset threshold is set to -74 dB.

The amplitude estimation was already described in previous works, where we detected a dynamic range lying around 35 and 40 dBs. The offsets are marked with a zero value. For the estimation of the spectral centroid, we use the object *centroid*, developed by T. Apel, J. Puterbaugh and D. Zicarelli. As the guitar notes do not present a steady spectrum, we choose the highest value occurring just after the onset detection. For the pitched events, we use a relative value for the centroid (centroid/fundamental); for the non-pitched events we set an absolute value in Hz.

In the acoustic guitar practice, slurring refers to the hammer-on and pull-off techniques, while *glissando* is performed by means of sliding a finger along one string. This does not produce a real glissando as in fretless instruments, but, instead, a sudden change in the frequency happens when the finger surpasses a fret. The slur flag is set when a new fundamental frequency is extracted without the detection of a new attack (or onset), what is mostly likely to occur with the use of the techniques just described.

We have not yet developed a complete tool for dealing with frequency variations occurring after the note onset. So far, the system is able to detect whether the fundamental frequency played on one string has suffered a variation beyond certain threshold once (bend) or more than two times (vibrato). The value of 8 cents has been used as the threshold, and is supported by experimental data collected in our lab [5]. It is necessary to limit the frequency variations to a wholeitone, otherwise variations due to resonances may be wrongly interpreted as vibrato or bend data. This information is stored by the offset event, since the vibrato or bend may happen anytime after the onset.

Our system still lacks tools dedicated to the handling of harmonics and sympathetic resonances – two very pregnant features of the guitar timbre. Besides, the percussive use of the guitar body also deserves a dedicated study.

In the near future, we also plan a systematic study of the accuracy of the system, dedicated to the low-level descriptors in use. This will be done on the Alhambra guitar, already mentioned in the paper, and also on a recent addition to the project: an instrument by Yamaha, equipped with

RMC pickups. The use of two instruments will provide an opportunity not only to refine the current parameters, but also to test the dependence of their settings on specific hardware configurations. Based on our previous experiments, we may say that the accuracy of the system depends not only on its physical components and algorithms, but also on the expertise of the players and on the musical content; all these variables must be taken in account for a fair evaluation of the system. For this paper, we had to correct up to 8% of the played notes in the worst case.

3. MID-LEVEL DESCRIPTORS

So far, the implemented mid-level descriptors may be divided into six categories: global, guitar-specific, rhythm, pitch, amplitude and spectrum descriptors.

3.1 Global Descriptors

The global descriptors are in number of three: duration, density of notes and 1/3-quantiles.

The duration of the segment is expressed in seconds, being measured between the first onset and the last offset. The density of notes is given by the ratio between the number of onsets and the duration. The 1/3-quantile descriptor expresses some basic temporal information about the distribution of onsets throughout the segment. The total duration of the segment is divided in three parts, and for each part we calculate the number of onsets. The descriptor's output comprises two values, one for the weight of the number of onsets in the first part, the other for the cumulative weight of the onsets in the first and second parts.

3.2 Guitar-specific Descriptors

3.2.1 Number of Used Strings – String "Centroid"

The number of used strings needs no further explanation; it is sufficient to remember that we are not taking in account the sympathetic resonances in the present study. We also calculate a vector with the number of onsets in each string. Based on this vector, it is possible to calculate a string "centroid", taking the weighted average of each item in the vector. To improve the selectivity of this centroid – once the same value may represent activity in the middle strings or in the outer strings – we add a second value, which calculates the contribution of strings 3 and 4 (in %) in the selected segment.

3.2.2 Fret Range – Open Strings (%) – Slur (%)

Given a pre-determined tuning for the guitar, it is possible to determine which frets were pressed by the left hand fingers during the performance. The fret range is calculated from the lower and upper limits of the frets explored in the segment under analysis. This value may be related to the longitudinal displacement of the left hand along the fretboard. Besides the range, the descriptor includes also the border values. The percentage of used open strings – in comparison to the total number of onsets – is a quite straightforward descriptor, which nevertheless may express an important feature of the musical texture

under analysis. The slur descriptor represents the percentage of onsets that were detected without a sharp attack, or, in other words, the percentage of onsets derived from hammer-on, pull-off and glissando gestures.

3.2.3 Presence of Block Chords

It is not a trivial task to detect the presence of chords in a segment. Chords may be played in different ways: at once (block chords or *plaqueé*), strummed, arpeggiated, or as *rasgueado*. For the definition of block chords, we opted for a somewhat arbitrary threshold of 30 ms: two onsets within this threshold are considered to belong to the same chord. This descriptor lists the chord sizes (in number of notes) found in the segment and their contribution (in % of "events"²) to the global texture.

3.2.4 String "Jump"

We call string "jump" the absolute value of the difference between the string indexes of two adjacent onsets. This jump can vary between the integers 0 and 5, and indicates the spatial proximity of two successive attacks. This descriptor is expressed by the mean value and the standard deviation found in each segment. Since the presence of block chords may somehow blur these results, it is also useful to calculate these values not taking the chords in account.

3.2.5 Periodicity of string indexes

The presence of periodicities in the sequence of string indexes may have a strong influence on the global gestalt of segments, and even on the gestalt of entire pieces. Before searching for periodicities, it is useful to replace the note indexes of a chord with a single index. In this way, 2-note chords indexes become the single index 20, 3-note chords indexes become 30, and so on. After this pre-processing stage, we calculate the average magnitude difference function (AMDF) of the list of indexes, using a window of 10 values (see equation 1). When the minima of this function are equally spaced, we may infer some sort of periodicity. If these minima are zero, we have an exact periodical exploration of string indexes. The descriptor's output consists of two lists, one with the minima values, the other with their spacing.

$$f(n) = \sum_{i=n+1}^{n+11} |x(i) - x(i - n)| \quad (1)$$

3.3 Rhythm Descriptors

3.3.1 Superimposition Index

The simultaneous sounding of different guitar strings is a central characteristic of this instrument. This may happen even during the play of a single melody in more than one string. The superimposition index returns a single value for each segment, and is calculated as follows: the durations (time intervals between onsets and offsets) of all notes are added together, and the resulting sum is then divided by the global duration of the segment.

² Note that here a chord is equaled to one event.

3.3.2 Most Prominent IOIs

In the analysis of the set of IOIs (inter-onset intervals) extracted from each segment, there is no intent to search for beats, rhythmic patterns or meter, for we are interested in a more generic rhythmic activity. This is due not only to the significant variations found in performances of even very simple rhythmic relations [1], but also to the chosen approach, mostly influenced by the guitar affordance and by some specific technical features.

As already mentioned, IOIs below 30 ms are considered to belong to a single chord. This is a reasonable but not definitive choice, for we are aware that it is possible to have more than six successive onsets fulfilling this condition. Fast tremolos on different strings, or *rasgueados*, may cause situations like this. In these cases, the algorithm must also take in account the string indexes and amplitudes, before the chord segmentation. On the other side, IOIs from fast tremolos, fast strummed chords and similar gestures are expected to occur within a threshold of 80 ms. The lower limit of 80 ms was chosen by two main reasons. Firstly, it represents the occurrence of 12.5 equally-spaced onsets in one second, which is a fair threshold for the conscious control of rhythmic values on the guitar, valid also for trills. Secondly, as the system runs in real-time, it prevents that the margin error surpasses 10% of the calculated IOIs.

IOIs larger than 80 ms are divided in seven ranges, following a 3/2 proportion; these ranges may be further subdivided, depending on their variance. After that, the system analyzes the proximity of the mean values in each range and may calculate a more appropriate mean value. Finally, the values whose weight stands above 5% are selected and depicted as the output of this descriptor.

We are aware that the procedure just described is somewhat naïf, founded on our own experience and intuition. A comparison with other methods –such as cluster analysis– might validate the results obtained so far, suggest its refinement or even the replacement of the procedure.

3.3.3 Presence of Silences

If the lack of activity on all strings surpasses 300 ms, we define this situation as a silence in the segment. The number of occurrences and their duration (in ms) are the outputs of this descriptor.

3.4 Pitch Descriptors

3.4.1 Pitch range – (Most) Used Pitch Classes

For each segment, we calculate the pitch range in semitones, and a vector holding the number of occurrences of each pitch class. Observing this vector, it is easy to say which pitch classes – and how many – are in use. A list with the two – or three – most used pitch classes is also depicted by this descriptor.

3.4.2 3-Note Prime Form

If the previous list has three elements, this descriptor returns the prime form attributed to their set by Forte's theory [6]. The prime forms dedicated to 3-note sets are rela-

tively small in number – 12 – and constitute an effective guide for an improvisation process on the guitar, along with the nominal pitch classes represented in the list³.

3.4.3 Non-Pitched Events – Vibrato – Bend

These descriptors express the percentage of occurrence of each of the listed features, in comparison to the total set of events played in the segment. These features may give a very distinctive character to the segment.

3.5 Amplitude and Spectrum Descriptors

These remaining descriptors are quite straightforward, and are represented by a mean value and its standard deviation. Note that only the pitched events are considered in the calculation of the mean value of the spectral centroid.

All extracted data is stored for further use, even if they are not displayed in the analysis main window. They may be used in the future variations processes.

Some of these descriptors are related to more than one category; it is sufficient to mention that the use of open strings has also effects on the pitch content, and that the superimposition index and the presence of chords – listed here as guitar-specific descriptors – are also important rhythm descriptors.

4. ANALYSIS OF FIVE EXCERPTS

Five short musical excerpts were chosen to illustrate the use of the mid-level descriptors discussed above. We have opted to present only one rendition for each excerpt – played by undergraduated guitarists – since the paper is focused on the implementation of descriptors, not on the comparison of performances. The excerpts are the following: I) the initial phrase of Bach’s *Bourrée* [8], a simple two-voice excerpt consisting of bass and melody lines (see Figure 1); II) the beginning of Brouwer’s *Études Simples II*, based on a choral texture, as depicted in Figure 3; III) the beginning of Villa-Lobos’s *Étude no. 1*, dedicated to *arpeggios* (see Figure 4); IV) the first section of Brouwer’s *Études Simples VII*, which explores fast notes with legatos (Figure 5); V) the beginning of Villa-Lobos’s *Prélude no. 4*, which presents a tenor melody interrupted now and then by chords (Figure 6). We will first point out the most distinguishing mid-level descriptors values for each excerpt, before proposing a more global and comparative approach.

The mid-level descriptors values for excerpt I (Bach’s *Bourrée*) can be seen in Figure 2. Despite the fact that a significant part of the values are self-explanatory, we would like to comment some of these results. The calculated string “centroid” is 3.55, but the contribution of strings 3 and 4 is only 20%, indicating a more intense use of both low and high strings. The (no-chords) string jump points to the use of the same or of neighbor strings in

³ In a different context, J. Bernard [7] justifies his analytical preference for trichords: “Groups of three pitches (trichords) are far more promising, for with trichords it is possible not only to define spatial configurations based on pairs of intervals but also to define relationships between trichords with a few simple operations. (...) However, even for tetrachords, the number of derivatives would increase to the point of being unwieldy.”

Figure 1. Beginning of J. S. Bach’s *Bourrée*, from the Suite for Lute in E-minor.

Figure 2. Mid-level descriptors for Bach’s *Bourrée* displayed in a Max window.

the disaccompanied notes. All two-note chords were detected, and also the two basic rhythmic values, which are in the proportion 1:2. The density of notes –4.35– is coherent with these values. The left hand remains in the first position, between frets 1 and 4. The most played pitch classes are G, E and F#, in this order. The superimposition index is 2.48, pointing to a more sustained voicing, which is also helped by the significant amount of open strings. The rendition does not present significant variations in amplitude and spectrum.

In Brouwer’s *Coral* (excerpt II), the 3-note chords represent 88% of the total events played. Only two most prominent pitch classes were indicated: G (with 11 occurrences) and D (with 8 occurrences). A tie between C, F and A occurred in the third position. The value 2.75 for the superimposition index may appear a bit surprising, since all chords have 3 notes. Despite that, we have observed in an earlier study [2] that block chords are hardly played without a considerable interruption between them, since we obtained a maximum value of 83% for the proportion between the sounding and the total (sounds + rests) parts. The two most prominent IOIs are 1626 and 771 ms, bearing a relation very close to 2:1.

The rendition of Villa-Lobos’s study of *arpeggios* (ex-

Étude II
Leo Brouwer

CORAL
Lento

Figure 3. Beginning of Brouwer's *Étude II* [9].

cerpt III) was made in a moderate tempo, resulting in a value of 181 ms for the one and only calculated IOI. As the excerpt is played with a fixed position for the left hand in every measure, the superimposition index is quite high: 5.56. The regularity of the sequence of the right hand fingers causes a value of 1.49 for the string jump, with a standard deviation of 0.5. The most played pitches are the E-minor triad, corresponding to the prime set (1 3 7). The spectrum descriptor showed a high standard deviation value: 6.49. The periodicity between every 16 onsets was also detected.

The analysis of Brouwer's seventh study (excerpt IV) detected the two interruptions present in the score, one with 468 ms and the other with 336 ms. These values point to a common tendency to accelerate towards the third (and longer) segment of the excerpt. The slur articulation was responsible for 25% of the onsets, while 2% of non-pitched onsets were also detected. As expected, the string jump is very low – 0.55 –, with a standard deviation of 0.99. With the exclusion of the last chord, this descriptor is even lower: 0.4.

Excerpt V (also by Villa-Lobos) presents the most varied rhythmic activity in this study. Two segments of silence were detected, measuring 1489 and 744 ms respectively. They are located after the third *pianissimo* chord in measures 2 and 4. The difference between the two values is due not only to the use of vibrato, rubatos and fermatas in this piece, but also to the very soft and sometimes irregular playing of these chords. Most prominent IOIs are 1489, 315, 499 and 230 ms, which may be related to the proportions 3/2:1/3:1/2:1/4. Vibrato was detected in 17% of the notes. The fret range is 12, measured between frets 3 and 14. Amplitude mean value is very low (-46 dB), with a considerable standard deviation (10 dB). The comparison between the two values related to string jumps reveals the melodic character of the non-chordal passages.

So far, our efforts in comparing different excerpts have three complementary strategies. The first is the search for pregnant features, like an intense exploration of non-pitched onset, legatos, vibratos, bends, open strings, periodicities, etc. The setting of the thresholds for this characterization demands a more definite context or a larger database than the one we are currently using.

The second strategy is the search for features that may express, in a very loose way, the musician's activity on the instrument during that excerpt. The presence of chords, their proportion to the total events and their types are a good

Étude Nº1
Étude des arpèges
Heitor Villa-Lobos

Allegro non troppo

Figure 4. Beginning of Villa-Lobos's *Étude no. 1* [10]

Étude VII
Leo Brouwer

Lo más rápido posible

Figure 5. Beginning of Leo Brouwer's *Étude VII* [9]

starting point. The most prominent IOIs and their proportions are also very important in this task. The density of events, string centroid and the superimposition index descriptors add further details. More specifically related to the left hand activity, we have also the descriptors related to fret exploration and pitch content.

A third concern is about regularity or homogeneity. As mid-level descriptors are based on averages, they are prone to hide discontinuities, interruptions, contrasts. Despite the presence of descriptors that may somehow express changing features – rhythmic quantiles, presence of silences, the string jumps, periodicity of string indexes –, their contribution is clearly very modest. On the other side, our automatic segmentation procedure, to be used in improvisational contexts, follows roughly the limits given by G. Lewis for the change of phrase behaviors in his *Voyager* system [12]: there is an assumption of homogeneity within segments ranging from 3 to 7 seconds. The excerpts presented here are significantly longer, and their heterogeneity could be better analyzed with shorter segments or with sliding windows.

Table 1 and Table 2 illustrate the potential and challenges of this kind of analysis. It is not difficult to detect a homogeneous arpeggio texture, as in excerpt III, but it is much more difficult to describe some details of excerpt V based only on these values. A larger database and the introduction of variation processes in this project will certainly bring new ideas and tools regarding discontinuities.

Figure 6. Beginning of Villa-Lobos's *Prélude no. 4* [11]

	chords types	IOIs (ms) (pauses)	density of notes (strings)	super. index (st. jump)
I	64% total 2-note(100%)	290 599	4.35 (6)	2.48 (2.59/0.5)
II	88% 3-note(100%)	1626 771	1.91 (5)	2.75 (1.48/1.0)
III	0%	181	5.48 (6)	5.56 (1.5/1.5)
IV	2% 2-note(100%)	159 197 (2 pauses)	4.87 (6)	1.33 (0.55/0.4)
V	18% 3-note(83%) 2-note(17%)	1489/315 489/230 (2 pauses)	1.35 (5)	1.48 (1.2/0.28)

Table 1. First set of mid-level descriptors values for the analyzed excerpts. Both string jump values –global and no-chords – are depicted.

5. FINAL REMARKS

The paper presented a series of mid-level descriptors related to the performance on an acoustic guitar, and their application in the analysis of a few selected excerpts. It is worth noting that many aspects not easily inferred from the excerpt's score are revealed through the analysis of its performance, although the small number of analyzed excerpts does not allow any generalizing attempt.

The preference for a non-stylistic approach does not exclude the incorporation of different algorithms already developed for tonality and metric detection, among others. For instance, beats could be acquired in real-time by means of beat tracking.

The development of a virtual player for interactive improvisation will also help refining the mid-level descriptors in use, and will certainly demand the enlargement of sound typologies and their corresponding low and mid-level descriptors.

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	frets	string centroid (open str.)	pitches prime form	1/3 and 2/3 quantiles
I	4 1–4	3.55 (40%)	G E F# (0 1 3)	0.47 0.81
II	3 1–3	3.18 (44%)	G D none	0.44 0.71
III	4 1–4	3.25 (48%)	E B G (0 3 7)	0.4 0.72
IV	7 1–7	3.08 (35%)	D B none	0.41 0.7
V	12 3–14	4.35 (52%)	E B none	0.34 0.66

Table 2. Second set of mid-level descriptors values for the analyzed excerpts.

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